

Report 150666

Overview	Name	[overload 150666] php-fpm
	Description	php-fpm
	Status	FINISHED
	Identity	ff6v5ooefc4f4fmpuazx
	Creation date	2025-02-10 20:55:32.850+00:00
	Start date	2019-01-04 12:04:43.684+00:00
	End date	2019-01-04 12:14:48.251+00:00
	Target	185.147.80.168:None
	Configuration	ff6cmbuqo6cpilclmw34

Case: overall

Density distribution of response times

Response time quantiles

	q50
	q75
	q80
	q85

Network response codes

HTTP response codes

Instances

Monitoring

Host ab61b3d4e7e718c27957cd5e6978f324

Memory

Net

System

cpu-cpu-total

diskio-vda1

diskio-vda2

net-eth0

netstat

Tables

Response time quantiles

Test	Case	q50	q75	q80	q85	q90	q95	q98	q99	q100
ff6v5ooefc4f4fmpuazx	overall	3.813	4.433	4.78	5.573	7.324	11.32	15.223	19.509	1005.657

Network response codes

Test	Case	0
ff6v5ooefc4f4fmpuazx	overall	57030

HTTP response codes

Test	Case	200
ff6v5ooefc4f4fmpuazx	overall	57030

Configurations

ff6cmbuqo6cpilclmw34

```

android:
  enabled: false
  package: yandextank.plugins.Android
  autostop:
    autostop: []
    enabled: true
    package: yandextank.plugins.Autostop
    report_file: autostop_report.txt
  bfg:
    enabled: false
    package: yandextank.plugins.Bfg
  console:
    cases_max_spark: 120
    cases_sort_by: count
    disable_all_colors: false
    disable_colors: ''
    enabled: true
    info_panel_width: 33
    max_case_len: 32
    package: yandextank.plugins.Console
    short_only: false
    sizes_max_spark: 120
    times_max_spark: 120
  core:
    affinity: ''
    artifacts_base_dir: ./logs
    artifacts_dir: null
    cmdline: /usr/local/bin/yandex-tank
    lock_dir: /var/lock/
    message: ''
    pid: 1
    taskset_path: taskset
    uuid: 0ec5e2c8-26d9-4044-83f7-f11b870e8ee8

```

```
influx:
enabled: false
package: yandextank.plugins.Influx
jmeter:
enabled: false
package: JMeter
json_report:
enabled: true
monitoring_log: monitoring.log
package: yandextank.plugins.JsonReport
test_data_log: test_data.log
overload:
api_address: https://overload.yandex.net/
api_attempts: 60
api_timeout: 10
chunk_size: 500000
component: ''
connection_timeout: 30
enabled: true
ignore_target_lock: false
job_dsc: php-fpm
job_name: php-fpm
jobno_file: jobno_file.txt
lock_targets: auto
log_data_requests: false
log_monitoring_requests: false
log_other_requests: false
log_status_requests: false
maintenance_attempts: 10
maintenance_timeout: 60
meta:
ammo_path: '/var/loadtest/ '
cmdline: /usr/local/bin/yandex-tank
jobno: 150666
loop_count: 57029
target_host: 185.147.80.168
target_port: 8000
network_attempts: 60
network_timeout: 10
notify: []
operator: null
package: yandextank.plugins.DataUploader
send_status_period: 10
strict_lock: false
target_lock_duration: 30m
task: ''
threads_timeout: 60
token_file: overload_token.txt
ver: ''
writer_endpoint: ''
phantom:
additional_libs: []
address: 185.147.80.168:8000
affinity: ''
ammo_limit: -1
ammo_type: phantom
ammofile: ''
autocases: 0
buffered_seconds: 2
cache_dir: null
chosen_cases: ''
client_certificate: ''
client_cipher_suites: ''
client_key: ''
config: ''
connection_test: true
```

```
enabled: true
enum_ammo: false
file_cache: 8192
force_stepping: 0
gatling_ip: ''
header_http: '1.0'
headers: []
instances: 1000
load_profile:
load_type: rps
schedule: line(1, 100, 60s) const(100, 540s)
loop: -1
method_options: ''
method_prefix: method_stream
multi: []
package: yandextank.plugins.Phantom
phantom_http_entity: 8M
phantom_http_field: 8K
phantom_http_field_num: 128
phantom_http_line: 1K
phantom_modules_path: /usr/lib/phantom
phantom_path: phantom
phout_file: ''
port: ''
source_log_prefix: ''
ssl: false
tank_type: http
threads: null
timeout: 11s
uris:

- /
  use_caching: true
  writelog: all
  rcassert:
    enabled: true
    fail_code: 10
    package: yandextank.plugins.RCAssert
    pass: ''
    rcheck:
      disk_limit: 2048
      enabled: true
      interval: 10s
      mem_limit: 512
      package: yandextank.plugins.ResourceCheck
    shellexec:
      catch_out: false
      enabled: true
      end: ''
      package: yandextank.plugins.ShellExec
      poll: ''
      post_process: ''
      prepare: ''
      start: ''
      telegraf:
        config: monitoring.xml
        config_contents: "<Monitoring>\n <Host address=\"185.147.80.168\" interval=\"1\" \
        \ username=\"ansible\">\n <CPU/> <Kernel/> <Net/> <System/> <Memory/>
        <Disk/>\
        \ <Netstat /> <Nstat/>\n </Host>\n</Monitoring>\n"
        default_target: localhost
        disguise_hostnames: true
        enabled: true
        kill_old: false
        package: yandextank.plugins.Telegraf
        ssh_timeout: 30s
```

